

Design of growth-coupled measurements of protease function

A proposal for onboarding proteases to the protein sequence-to-function measurement platform.

- Uses a gene circuit to tie protease activity to bacterial cell growth that relies on cleavage of lysozyme from a T7 RNAP
- Calibration variants span the dynamic range of activity enable quantitative function measurements
- First dataset collection will focus on TEV proteases.

This document was created as a part of the Pooled, Growth-Based Assays for Protein Function Measurements pipeline¹ for Align to Innovate's Open Dataset Initiative. Align to Innovate is a non-profit research organization operating under open science principles with the goal of improving science research with programmable experiments. The Open Datasets Initiative is working to accelerate community-driven science with the use of automated labs to pioneer robust data collection methods and curated, high-fidelity, public biological datasets amenable to machine learning. This work was supported by Align to Innovate's Open Datasets Initiative which receives philanthropic funding in part from Griffin Catalyst.

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Context, Significance, and Impact

Proteases are interesting targets for dataset collection, and protease substrate specificity has particularly interesting applications to human health. Previous work has demonstrated the ability to evolve proteases with altered specificity relevant to hepatitis C², botulinum neurotoxin³, and systemic challenges such as pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-23⁴. Drugs that inhibit activity of particular proteases in the body have long existed to target HIV, hepatitis C, and other infectious diseases.

AlphaFold⁵ and RoseTTAFold⁶ have demonstrated the ability to predict protein-protein interactions (PPIs) with higher accuracy than other types of protein-substrate interactions, and it is possible to strategically design input libraries for this approach by leveraging these tools. Docking algorithms, such as High

Ambiguity Driven protein-protein DOCKing (HADDOCK)⁷ have been developed specifically to infer which residues between two proteins are likely to be physically interacting. Thus, powerful models currently exist for examining protease systems.

Proteases act on peptide substrates rather than small molecules. This offers the opportunity to explore mutational space in both the protease and/or its substrate. This, in turn, will enable us to develop a greater understanding of how enzyme function may be influenced by such parameters. To this end, mutational diversity in both tobacco etch virus (TEV) protease and its seven-amino-acid substrate will be explored, and their activities will be compared to previously-defined benchmark library members.

Protease Circuit

Protease substrate specificity^{3,4} can be transduced into gene expression by co-expressing the protease of interest together with a T7 RNAP fused to lysozyme with the target sequence in between (Fig. C1). Only when the protease is functional will it free the T7 RNAP from its inhibitor, thus enabling gene expression.

Here, a previously validated protease-mediated genetic circuit is built upon by linking protease cleavage activity and specificity to host antibiotic resistance (Fig. C2). Additionally, the protease genes of interest (GOI) will be expressed as maltose binding protein (MBP) fusions to improve solubility.

Proposed Host and Plasmids

The *E. coli* strain DH10B was chosen for this protease dataset due to its relatively high transformation efficiency and widespread use in synthetic biology. We are also interested in characterizing variants in [S2060](#), a strain of *E. coli* optimized for use in continuous directed evolution experiments. Initial plasmid designs for the protease assay are given below. This includes one plasmid for each of the proposed AbR genes:

Link to Benchling for TetA:

<https://benchling.com/s/seq-Nd0fAewjRRsocytZKOzp?m=slm-A88bpMnGQmK1Rv0w92lk>

Link to Benchling for Zeo:

<https://benchling.com/s/seq-eQHDxvsZj4c0EPQpTmii?m=slm-RJ7JDpqTOKQEokQOwP2s>

Proposed Controls for Assay Development

We will use the TEV protease to onboard the protease function plasmid. TEV protease exhibits greater substrate specificity than many other proteases by uniquely recognizing the seven amino acid sequence ENLYFQS and cleaving between Q and S. TEV protease has been subject to natural evolutionary pressure as an important agent in processing viral polypeptides, paramount to the virus's function and propagation. This protease has also been engineered, evolved, and highly characterized in laboratory settings, but there are several questions about its specificity that have yet to be explored. The growth-based assays approach can eventually be used to examine increasing or changing specificity of other proteases.

The Crick Institute team has existing data about protease and substrate variants measured with their in-house, two-plasmid system. They have data for six protease variants (single G insertion mutants) against the native substrate, and 10 substrate variants against the native (WT) TEV protease, showing that varying position P1'(S) and P2(F) of the substrate alters the amount of activity most.

Stage 1 - Development and Tuning

The protease-substrate sequence combinations listed in [Table C1](#) below cover high, medium, and low functional outputs, relative to WT protease (high) activity, and are currently used in the Crick team's protease circuit that utilizes 2-plasmid circuitry.

A key step here will be to determine if similar activity outputs are obtained from a one-plasmid design in order to define the dynamic range of this system. It is critical that a sufficient dynamic range is established such that large and diverse libraries of variants can be pooled and assayed effectively. Given that a one-plasmid system has been designed, this may require further tuning of the promoter/RBS sequences upstream of the T7-RNAP reporter cassette. Furthermore, each

substrate variant may benefit from a different set of promoters to ensure an acceptable dynamic range can be accessed.

To begin, plasmid variants will be cloned that contain three different promoters, of varying relative strengths, upstream of the reporter cassette ([Fig. C3](#)). In addition, for each of these three promoters, two further versions will be cloned, each containing either a high or low strength RBS. The dynamic range of readout for these six constructs will be determined across a range of antibiotic concentrations for three different protease variants representing high to low activity. The hope is to identify RBS and promoter combinations which give rise to the best sensitivity for a given protease activity.

Stage 2 - Normalization and Calibration Controls

In addition to the variants listed below ([Table C2](#)), a larger diversity of variants will be investigated by cloning an ePCR library of TEV protease, screening colonies against several substrates, and picking additional variants. If this is insufficient to densely cover the relevant dynamic range, a combinatorial substrate library that varies P1'(S) and P2(F) will be cloned.

Substrate (action site)	Protease variant (GOI)	Expected activity
ENLYFQS (WT substrate)	WT TEV	High activity
ENLYFQS (WT substrate)	TEV2	Low activity
ENLYFQA	WT TEV	Medium activity
ENLYFQS (WT substrate)	C151A	Inactive (zero activity)

Table C1: Protease and substrate pairs to be used during Stage 1.

Figure C3: Proposed plate map for Stage 1.

Substrate (action site)	Protease variant (GOI)	Expected activity	Type of control
ENLYFQS (WT substrate)	WT TEV	High activity	Normalization
ENLYFQS (WT substrate)	TEV5	High activity	Normalization
ENLYFQS (WT substrate)	TEV2	Low activity	Calibration
ENLYFQS (WT substrate)	C151A	Inactive (zero activity)	Calibration
ENLY W QS	WT TEV	High activity	Calibration
ENL M FQS	WT TEV	High activity	Calibration
F NLYFQS	WT TEV	Medium high activity	Calibration
ENLYFQ M	WT TEV	Medium high activity	Calibration
ENLYFQ A	WT TEV	Medium activity	Calibration
ENLYFQ Y	WT TEV	Low or zero activity	Calibration

Table C2: Protease and substrate pairs to be used during Stage 2.

Pilot-Scale Collection: Tobacco Etch Virus (TEV) Protease

Similar to the Transcription Factor pilot, three substrates against 30,000 sequence variants will be run for the TEV protease WT. This split was chosen to maximize protease diversity, as the goal of the eventual predictive model will be to design the best protease for a given substrate sequence.

Figure C4: Strategy for selecting protein targets for the protease dataset.

Large-Scale Collection: TEV Protease Structural Homologs and Non-Canonical Substrates

As the growth-based assay continues to develop, the same pipeline can be applied to areas that are relevant for therapeutics. There is potential to diversify the therapeutic applications in proteases both by engineering within the substrate solution space as well as the protease solution space. By generating single-mutants of known protease substrates, near-neighbors of relevant protease sequences can be explored as potential agents to cleave these new, non-canonical substrates. In order to broadly explore

the larger landscape of protease genotypes, combinatorial libraries of proteases that contain structural homologues to TEV protease will be created. This will start with looking at structural similarity between TEV and serine proteases, such as subtilisin, and the mammalian protease trypsin. Overall, the first bolus of data in the dataset should be diversified both in the substrate dimension (focusing on clinically-relevant substrates) and in the protease dimension (focusing on structurally homologous proteins).

References

1. Cortade, D., d'Oelsnitz, S., Chadha, A., Hayes, O., Taghon, G., Doerr, M., Born, S., Kelly, P., Ross, D., DeBenedictis, E., & Align to Innovate. Design of a generalized platform for gathering protein sequence → function datasets at scale. (2024) doi:10.5281/zenodo.12521641
2. Dickinson, B. C., Packer, M. S., Badran, A. H. & Liu, D. R. A system for the continuous directed evolution of proteases rapidly reveals drug-resistance mutations. *Nat. Commun.* **5**, 5352 (2014).
3. Blum, T. R. *et al.* Phage-assisted evolution of botulinum neurotoxin proteases with reprogrammed specificity. *Science* **371**, 803–810 (2021).
4. Packer, M. S., Rees, H. A. & Liu, D. R. Phage-assisted continuous evolution of proteases with altered substrate specificity. *Nat. Commun.* **8**, 956 (2017).
5. Jumper, J. *et al.* Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold. *Nature* **596**, 583–589 (2021)
6. Baek, M. *et al.* Accurate prediction of protein structures and interactions using a three-track neural network. *Science* **373**, 871–876 (2021)
7. Dominguez, C., Boelens, R. & Bonvin, A. M. J. J. HADDOCK: a protein-protein docking approach based on biochemical or biophysical information. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **125**, 1731–1737 (2003).